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Artificial Intelligence and Discourse Makers in English

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Abstract: The paper tries to investigate the connection between AI and the people who make the discourse in English is a complicated one with many facets. The following objectives are set to achieve the aim of the paper: Shed light on Ethics and the Use of Discourse Makers in English; Morals and new media. The methods of the research are quantitative and qualitative. Frequency analysis, discourse analysis, and other methods will be used to study our corpora.

Keywords: AI, DMs, NLP, Ethics, Morals, Media

Introduction

The connection between AI and the people who make the discourse in English is a complicated one with many facets. On the one hand, AI algorithms have the potential to be utilized in order to improve readability and enhance the efficiency of discourse creators in the English language. On the other side, the rising utilization of AI in the production of content raises problems regarding the authenticity and legitimacy of discourse makers.

Natural language processing (NLP) algorithms are one use of artificial intelligence that can be helpful to those who construct speech (Jones et al. 6). These algorithms can be applied to the analysis of text

in order to locate places in which the readability of the text can be enhanced. For instance, you can use them to identify complicated language structures, an excessive amount of jargon, and other characteristics that can make it difficult to understand something. AI algorithms can assist discourse creators in producing content that is more approachable and engaging by identifying these challenges and providing solutions to them.

The aim of this paper is to:

1. Shed light on Ethics and the Use of Discourse Makers in English
2. Morals and new media

The employment of algorithms that generate content is another way that AI can be of assistance to those who are creating dialogue. These algorithms can be used to automatically generate material based on templates or rules that have been set in advance. For example, you can use them to produce headlines, summaries, or even whole articles with them. Discourse creators can save time and resources by automating these procedures, all while maintaining a consistent style and tone in their work. The growing use of AI in the production of content raises issues about the authenticity and legitimacy of those who generate discourse. It is becoming increasingly difficult to differentiate between information that was written by humans and content that was made by computers as AI algorithms continue to advance in their level of sophistication. Because of this, the readers' trust in the authors of the discourse can be damaged, and the influence of their work can be lessened.

In addition to this, the implementation of AI in the production of material has the potential to increase preexisting prejudices and disparities. For instance, if AI algorithms are trained on data that displays prejudiced or discriminating ideas, then it is possible that such prejudices will be reproduced in the material that the algorithms generate. This can result in the continuation of harmful stereotypes as well as practices that exclude certain groups.

In spite of these issues, there is a substantial possibility that AI and the makers of discourse might collaborate in order to produce material that is of high quality, easily accessible and that both engages and informs readers. Discourse makers are able to develop material that is more successful and influential than either human creativity or machine intelligence could achieve on their own by harnessing the capabilities of both of these factors in their work.

Ultimately, the interaction between AI and the creators of discourse in English is intricate and fraught with a variety of complexities. Concerns concerning authenticity, legitimacy, and bias have been raised in relation to artificial intelligence (AI), despite the fact that it has the potential to be a useful tool for strengthening the effectiveness of discourse producers and improving readability. As the field of artificial intelligence continues to advance, it will be essential for those who shape the discourse to give careful consideration to the part that technology plays in their work and to make certain that they uphold the highest possible standards of both quality and ethics.

Ethics and the Use of Discourse Makers in English

Discourse markers play such an important part in the process of creating and comprehending language, the use of them raises problems about morality. Linguists have a responsibility to consider the effects that discourse markers have on both individuals and communities, particularly when those discourse markers are used to uphold negative views or stereotypes. Discourse markers, such as the use of "uh" or "like" to imply that another person is unintelligent, are one example of how racial or gendered stereotypes can be reinforced through the use of language.

Linguists need to take into consideration a number of different factors, one of which is power relations in the deployment of discourse markers. The use of certain discourse markers might be misconstrued as an effort to dominate or exert control over the discussion, and this is especially true in circumstances in which one individual or group possesses a greater amount of social or cultural capital than another. This can generate sentiments of alienation and exclusion in persons who are not familiar with the meaning of the discourse markers in question or do not share those indicators themselves.

The manner in which discourse markers are utilised may also have an impact on the ethics of research. Researchers have a responsibility to ensure that they obtain the informed permission of participants and that they do nothing to jeopardise or harm people through the manipulation of language use. This is of utmost importance in studies involving minors as well as individuals whose cognitive or linguistic abilities are impaired, as participants in these types of studies may be more vulnerable or have less agency.

Linguists should use extreme caution when employing discourse markers and give serious consideration to the potential repercussions of doing so in light of the ethical concerns that have been raised. If researchers want to apply inclusive and respectful discourse markers that are aimed at empowering individuals and groups, they first need to be aware of the power dynamics that are at play in the use of language. When researchers find evidence that the use of particular discourse markers is contributing to the perpetuation of harmful attitudes or stereotypes, they should work to question dominant narratives and advance more inclusive and equitable modes of communication. In addition, they should work to advance more inclusive and equitable modes of communication.

Morals and new media

When utilised in modern media such as social networks, online discussion boards, and electronic discourse, discourse markers give rise to new ethical problems. The use of emoticons, hashtags, and acronyms are all examples of discourse markers, and they have a significant impact on online communication. Yet, there may be ethical problems with its implementation because there are difficulties of veracity, exclusion, and secrecy.

When it comes to ethical considerations, accuracy is of the utmost importance when employing discourse markers in digital media. In written or electronic communication, discourse markers are

used frequently to express the attitude or feeling of the speaker. Yet, the participants' cultural backgrounds as well as the surrounding surroundings may cause some difference in how they interpret these signals. Failure to correctly perceive or communicate discourse markers can lead to a variety of problems, including disagreements, misunderstandings, and the spread of incorrect information. Users of digital platforms have an obligation to consider the likelihood of misunderstandings and strive for greater specificity in their use of discourse markers in order to increase the likelihood that their communications will be understood in the manner in which they were intended.

When it comes to ethical considerations involving the utilisation of discourse markers in new media, inclusion should take precedence. Depending on the discourse markers that are utilised, the manner in which people communicate with one another online may either be more or less inviting of individuals from a variety of backgrounds and points of view. When certain speech indicators are utilised, it is possible for individuals who come from a variety of racial, ethnic, religious, linguistic, or socioeconomic backgrounds to be excluded from dialogues. Users of new media have a responsibility to be aware of the implications of excluding people and to make concerted efforts to incorporate them into the discussions they have with others by employing a wide range of inclusive discourse markers in their writing and in their spoken communication.

The use of discourse markers in new media raises moral concerns regarding the invasion of personal space. When the usage of discourse markers such as hashtags and location identifiers reveals the whereabouts and activities of persons, there is a justifiable basis for concerns pertaining to privacy and security. Users of new media should be aware of the potential risks to their privacy that are linked with the use of discourse markers, and they should take the appropriate safeguards to protect not just their own personal information but also the personal information of others.

The utilization of discourse markers in contemporary media gives rise to additional worries relating to the gathering of data and the processing of algorithms. When algorithms use discourse markers for data analysis, sentiment analysis, or content suggestion, ethical considerations around data privacy, permission, and algorithmic biases occur. When using discourse markers, consumers of modern media would be well to give some thought to the context of data collection and algorithmic processing.

Table 1

Ethical Considerations

Ethical Considerations	News Media	Entertainment Media
Accuracy	The data, facts, and events that are presented by the discourse markers in the	Congruence is required to exist between the discourse markers used in a piece of

	<p>news media ought to be presented in an open and honest manner. Misunderstandings, prejudice, and disagreements are all potential outcomes of incorrectly using or interpreting discourse markers in a conversation.</p>	<p>entertainment media and the tone, mood, and genre that are intended to be conveyed by the work. The improper or careless use of discourse markers can lead to a variety of problematic outcomes, including misrepresentation, stereotyping, and cultural appropriation.</p>
Inclusivity	<p>Language markers should be used by media sources in a way that is both open to and respectful of the diverse identities, cultures, and points of view that exist in the world. Reporters have a responsibility to avoid employing speech markers that can be construed in a way that is discriminatory or exclusive if they want to promote diversity and inclusion in the news.</p>	<p>It is important for those working in the entertainment sector to be aware of the consequences of the discourse markers they use. It is necessary to abstain from using language that is cruel, discriminatory, or insulting if one wishes to encourage acceptance and understanding of the many different groups and identities that exist.</p>
Privacy	<p>The identification of individuals, their locations, or the activities they are engaged in should not be divulged through the use of discourse markers in the media because this could put them in danger. While reporting the news, discourse markers should be utilised with caution to safeguard people's privacy and avoid betraying their faith in the media.</p>	<p>It is of the utmost importance that, in this day and age of social media and online interactions, entertainment media refrain from using discourse markers that may put users' privacy at risk or do not have their consent. In today's popular culture, the utilisation of discourse markers is always required to be carried out with the person's knowledge and permission.</p>
Data Processing	<p>Discourse markers are often used in the news media, and algorithms could process these markers to do data analysis, sentiment analysis, and content suggestion. Protecting the privacy of users of discourse markers, gaining informed consent, and addressing the possibility for algorithmic prejudice are all important ethical factors that should be taken into account when using discourse markers in the media.</p>	<p>Processing discourse markers used in entertainment media can also be done by algorithms, which can then be used to make content recommendations, create user profiles, or show targeted adverts. When it comes to the use of discourse markers in forms of entertainment media, there are a variety of moral considerations that need to be taken into account.</p>

Conclusion

One way that artificial intelligence (AI) can be used to evaluate the readability of information in the entertainment media is by analyzing the language used by discourse creators such as bloggers and influencers. For example, making the text more legible by using simpler words and shorter phrases is something that can be done, and artificial intelligence can be trained to recognize these patterns. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) to assess the readability of content produced by the entertainment sector is one method by which its messages could potentially reach more people.

Moreover, AI can be used to customize the reading experience of each individual user to their unique skill set. This is accomplished by assessing the user's current reading level and presenting content that is appropriate for that level. In order to accomplish this goal, the user's reading preferences can be assessed in order to make recommendations for personally relevant information. This strategy has two distinct benefits: first, it increases the enjoyment of reading, and second, it lessens the risk that readers would become irritated by content that is above their grasp.

An additional application for artificial intelligence (AI) is the evaluation of content to determine its readability and the provision of feedback to those who create discourse. By analyzing linguistic patterns and providing recommendations for their improvement, AI can provide creators of discourse with assistance in expanding their audience base. Because of this, the people who create the discourse and the people who consume it may experience improvements in their ability to communicate with one another and a strengthening of their connection.

Further study can investigate how algorithms affect the selection and placement of discourse markers in online writing. A large-scale quantitative study comparing the prevalence of different discourse indicators in marketed and unpromoted content is one such approach. The amount to which algorithms affect content authors' language decisions could be gleaned from such a study.

Research into the impact of discourse markers on content performance across digital platforms is possible. One technique could be a qualitative analysis of discourse cues in both virally effective and unsuccessful content. A deeper understanding of the relationship between discourse markers and content performance might help authors make more strategic use of language.

Discourse markers may be employed differently across social media platforms, which calls for more research into the topic. Articles published for news websites and those written for social media platforms, for example, can be compared with regards to their use of discourse markers. This type of research has the ability to shed light on the diverse linguistic needs of online subcultures.

Given the potential effects of discourse markers on how one should understand a piece of writing, studies on the moral dimensions of content generation via algorithms are also pertinent. This could be achieved by a qualitative investigation into the ways in which particular speech indicators contribute to the spread of misinformation and the reinforcement of unfavourable stereotypes. If

artists are conscious of these moral factors, they can make more informed decisions about the language they use in their creations.

In conclusion, the utilization of AI in conjunction with discourse makers has the potential to raise both the readability and interest levels of various forms of entertainment media. By keeping an eye on readability, tailoring the reading experience, and providing feedback to discourse producers, AI can help make information more accessible to a greater number of people and more effective at conveying ideas.

Further research is needed in order to get a better understanding of how artificial intelligence (AI) can be used to improve the role of discourse makers in the media. The primary focus of research in this field should be on the development of AI-enabled tools and platforms that are geared toward streamlining the process by which discourse makers are included in the media and entertainment sectors. Also, the research should look into ways to solve the ethical concerns that are brought up by the application of AI in question and take them into consideration.

When it comes to the fast-expanding sector of utilizing discourse makers in the news media and entertainment, there are exciting new opportunities and interesting new difficulties on the horizon. Despite the fact that the studies that we analyzed for this paper provided light on the subject of AI and discourse makers in the media, there is still a significant amount of ground to cover. If we continue to delve into this area, we will be able to gain additional knowledge regarding the impact that AI and discourse makers have on public discourse and opinion.

References

- Aijmer, K. (2002). *English discourse particles*. John Benjamins Publishing.
- Brinton, L. J., & Traugott, E. C. (2005). *Lexicalization and language change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Di Ferrante, L. (2021). Transitioning between small talk and work talk through discourse markers: Evidence from a workplace spoken corpus. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 7-30.
- Eggins, S., & Slade, D. (1997). *Analyzing casual conversation*. Cassell.
- Faisal, W. M. The discourse marker (Well) in selected talk shows: A discourse analysis study.
- Fraser, B. (1990). An approach to discourse markers. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 14(3), 383-398.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1975). Learning how to mean. In *Foundations of language development* (pp. 239-265). Academic Press.
- Jiang, L., & Gu, M. M. (2022). Understanding youths' civic participation online: A digital multimodal composing perspective. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 47(4), 537-556.

- Lakoff, R. (1973). The logic of politeness; or, minding your p's and q's. In *Papers from the Ninth Regional Meeting* (pp. 292-305). Chicago Linguistic Society.
- Nilsson, B., & Carlsson, E. (2014). Swedish politicians and new media: Democracy, identity and populism in a digital discourse. *New Media & Society*, 16(4), 655-671.
- Pedroni, M. (2022). Two decades of fashion blogging and influencing: A critical overview. *Fashion Theory*, 1-32.
- Rhee, S. (2020). On determinants of discourse marker functions: Grammaticalization and discourse-analytic perspectives. *Linguistic Research*, 37(2), 289-325.
- Rone, J. (2022). Far right alternative news media as 'indignation mobilization mechanisms': How the far right opposed the Global Compact for Migration. *Information, Communication & Society*, 25(9), 1333-1350.
- Schiffrin, D. (1987). *Discourse markers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Schiffrin, D. (2005). Discourse markers: Language, meaning, and context. In *The Handbook of Discourse Analysis* (pp. 54-75).
- Schourup, L. (1985). *Common discourse particles in English conversation* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of California, Los Angeles.
- Shirazi, F. (2013). Social media and the social movements in the Middle East and North Africa: A critical discourse analysis. *Information Technology & People*.
- Tagliamonte, S. A. (2006). *Analysing sociolinguistic variation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Uzunoğlu, E., & Misci Kip, S. (2014). Brand communication through digital influencers: Leveraging blogger engagement. *International Journal of Information Management*, 34(5), 592-602.